

A Multi-Indicator Assessment of Soil Degradation Under Contrasting Land Use Systems in Coastal Plain Sands of Imo State Southeastern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: Soil degradation remains a major constraint to sustainable land management in tropical ecosystems, particularly in regions undergoing rapid land use transformation. This study applied a multi-indicator approach to evaluate soil degradation under four contrasting land use systems—oil palm plantation, secondary forest, industrial layout, and residential areas—within the Coastal Plain Sands of Imo State, Southeastern Nigeria. Eight profile pits were excavated, and thirty-seven soil samples were collected across genetic horizons for the analysis of selected physicochemical properties and degradation indices, including dispersion ratio (DR), clay dispersion ratio (CDR), clay flocculation index (CFI), clay dispersion index (CDI), structural stability index (S), exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP), and sodium adsorption ratio (SAR). Results revealed significant variation in soil quality across land uses. Industrial and residential soils exhibited higher bulk density (1.64–1.73 Mg m⁻³), lower total porosity (35.16–38.16%), and reduced soil organic carbon (0.34–0.54 g kg⁻¹) compared to secondary forest soils. Dispersion indices were consistently above critical thresholds (DR: 0.46–0.85), indicating widespread susceptibility to structural breakdown, while structural stability values remained very low (S: 0.22–0.72), reflecting severe physical degradation. In contrast, secondary forest soils showed relatively improved aggregation and soil condition. Although ESP (2.11–4.33%) and SAR (0.11–0.24) were below sodicity thresholds, elevated dispersion and low structural stability indicate increasing vulnerability to degradation. In conclusion, soil degradation followed the gradient: secondary forest < oil palm plantation < residential layout < industrial layout. The findings demonstrate that degradation is primarily driven by compaction and organic matter depletion rather than sodicity. The multi-indicator framework proved effective in capturing the complexity of soil degradation and provides a robust basis for sustainable soil management in fragile tropical soils.

KEYWORDS: Soil degradation, Land use systems, multi-indicator approach, Soil physicochemical properties, Coastal Plain Sands

INTRODUCTION

Soil degradation is a critical global environmental challenge with far-reaching implications for food security, ecosystem services, and climate resilience. It is estimated that nearly one-third of the world's soils are already degraded, with the extent expected to increase as population growth intensifies pressure on land resources¹. In sub-Saharan Africa, soil degradation remains a major constraint to agricultural productivity, exacerbating poverty and reducing the resilience of farming systems². In Nigeria, rapid population growth and expanding urbanization have accelerated land use changes, exposing soils to deforestation, intensive cultivation, infrastructure development, and other anthropogenic disturbances that compromise soil quality^{3,4}.

Land use systems are among the most significant drivers of soil degradation, as they directly influence soil physical, chemical, and biological processes. Natural ecosystems such as forests generally maintain higher soil organic matter, better aggregation, and more efficient nutrient cycling due to continuous litter input and minimal disturbance⁵. In contrast, agricultural, industrial, and residential land uses often result in soil compaction, organic matter depletion, reduced porosity, and structural instability⁶. These effects are particularly pronounced in soils derived from Coastal Plain Sands, which are inherently fragile due to their coarse texture, low nutrient reserves, weak structural development, and high susceptibility to erosion. Under conditions of high rainfall and unregulated land conversion, such soils are highly vulnerable to rapid degradation⁷.

Despite the recognized sensitivity of Coastal Plain Sands, there remains limited integrative, site-specific evidence on how contrasting land use systems influence soil degradation processes in southeastern Nigeria. Most existing studies have focused on individual indicators such as soil organic carbon or bulk density, which do not adequately capture the complex and multi-dimensional nature of soil degradation. Furthermore, the combined application of structural and sodicity-related indices including dispersion ratio (DR), clay dispersion ratio (CDR), clay flocculation index (CFI), clay dispersion index (CDI), structural stability index (S),

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exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP), and sodium adsorption ratio (SAR) has received limited attention in tropical agro-ecosystems. The lack of such integrated assessments restricts a comprehensive understanding of degradation mechanisms and limits the development of effective soil management strategies⁸.

Owerri, the capital of Imo State in southeastern Nigeria, represents a rapidly urbanizing landscape where agricultural and natural lands are increasingly converted into residential and industrial uses. This transition exerts significant pressure on soil resources, particularly within the Coastal Plain Sands ecosystem, where degradation processes can be accelerated by both natural and anthropogenic factors. Understanding the extent and drivers of soil degradation across different land use systems in this environment is therefore essential for sustainable land management and policy formulation⁹.

Against this background, this study employs a multi-indicator framework to assess soil degradation under four contrasting land use systems: oil palm plantation, secondary forest, industrial layout, and residential areas, in the Coastal Plain Sands of Imo State, southeastern Nigeria. Specifically, the study aims to: (i) evaluate the extent and variability of soil degradation using selected physicochemical properties and degradation indices; (ii) examine the relationships between soil properties and degradation indices; and (iii) provide an integrated basis for soil quality assessment and sustainable land management in fragile tropical environments.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted in selected locations within Owerri, Imo State, southeastern Nigeria, namely Obinze, Avu, Irete, and Amakohia. The area lies between latitudes 5°28'35" N and 5°49'05" N, and longitudes 7°01'33" E and 7°10'05" E, with elevations ranging from 57 to 145 m above sea level. The region falls within the humid tropical rainforest zone and is characterized by a bimodal rainfall pattern, with annual precipitation ranging from 2,500 to 3,000 mm. The wet season extends from April to November, while the dry season occurs between December and March. Mean annual temperature ranges from 28°C to 31°C, with minimal seasonal variation¹⁰.

The soils are derived from Coastal Plain Sands and are typically sandy to sandy clay loam in texture, inherently low in nutrient reserves, weakly structured, and highly susceptible to erosion and degradation under intensive land use⁷. The study area has undergone significant anthropogenic modification due to agricultural activities, urban expansion, and industrial development.

Land Use Systems

Four contrasting land use systems were selected based on their dominance and intensity: oil palm plantation (OP) at Obinze, secondary forest (SF) at Avu, industrial layout (IL) at Irete, and residential layout (RL) at Amakohia.

The oil palm plantation (>15 years old) is dominated by *dura* and *tenera* varieties and is situated on gentle slopes (0–2%) with evidence of periodic mechanical disturbance. The secondary forest (>25 years old) is characterized by dense vegetation cover, a well-developed litter layer, and minimal anthropogenic interference. The industrial layout (>30 years old) comprises clusters of manufacturing activities and exhibits extensive land surface modification, compaction, and infrastructural development. The residential layout (>40 years old) is marked by continuous construction activities, land leveling, and increasing population pressure. Across all sites, geomorphic features include gentle slopes, evidence of sheet erosion, and moderately well-drained conditions.

Soil Sampling and Field Description

A targeted sampling approach was adopted to capture representative areas exhibiting visible signs of soil degradation. Two profile pits were excavated in each land use system, resulting in a total of eight profile pits. Soil profile descriptions were carried out according to FAO¹¹ guidelines, including horizon identification and morphological characterization. A total of thirty-seven soil samples were collected from genetic horizons within the profiles. Samples were air-dried, gently crushed, and sieved through a 2 mm mesh prior to laboratory analysis.

Laboratory Analyses

Standard analytical procedures were employed to determine soil physicochemical properties. Particle size distribution was determined using the hydrometer method¹², while bulk density was measured using the core method¹³. Soil moisture content was determined by oven-drying, and soil pH was measured in a 1:2.5 soil-to-water suspension¹⁵.

Soil organic carbon (SOC) was determined using the wet oxidation method¹⁶, and total nitrogen (TN) was analyzed using the micro-Kjeldahl method¹⁷. Available phosphorus was determined using the Bray I method¹⁸. Exchangeable acidity was determined following standard procedures¹⁹, while exchangeable bases (Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺, Na⁺) were extracted using ammonium acetate²⁰. Cation exchange capacity (CEC) was determined using the ammonium acetate method²¹.

Soil Degradation Indices

Soil degradation was assessed using a multi-indicator approach incorporating structural and sodicity-related indices. Exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) and sodium adsorption ratio (SAR) were calculated following standard procedures²². Clay dispersion

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indices, including dispersion ratio (DR)²³, clay dispersion ratio (CDR), clay flocculation index (CFI), and clay dispersion index (CDI), were computed using established methods.

The soil structural stability index (S) was calculated following Pieri²⁴, where values < 5 indicate severe degradation, 5–7 high degradation, 7–9 moderate stability, and > 9 stable conditions. An overall Soil Degradation Rating (SDR) was derived based on the framework proposed by Lal²⁵ to integrate multiple indicators into a composite assessment of soil quality (Table 1).

Data Analysis

Data were subjected to descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, and range, using the R statistical software²⁶. All visualizations were generated using ggplot2²⁷ and exported in high-resolution PNG formats using ggsave().

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Soil degradation indices exhibited pronounced variability across land use systems and profile depths (Tables 2 and 3; Figures 1–3), reflecting the combined influence of land use intensity, organic matter dynamics, and anthropogenic disturbance. Dispersion ratio (DR) ranged from 0.46 to 0.85, with mean values exceeding the critical threshold of 0.30 across all profiles, indicating widespread susceptibility to aggregate breakdown and erosion. High DR values are characteristic of dispersive soils with weak structural integrity and high erodibility.²⁵ Although relatively high DR values were also observed in secondary forest soils, their structural stability was maintained due to the mitigating effects of higher organic matter content and improved aggregation.

Similarly, clay dispersion ratio (CDR), which reached values as high as 0.71 in industrial soils, indicates that structural degradation extends beyond surface horizons into the subsoil, potentially impairing permeability and root penetration. The clay flocculation index (CFI) ranged from 0.59 to 0.68, suggesting a moderate inherent capacity for aggregation; however, this potential appears to be suppressed in disturbed systems due to anthropogenic influences. Clay dispersion index (CDI) values were highest in industrial layouts (up to 0.41), reflecting greater clay dispersion and reduced aggregate stability^{32,33}. In contrast, secondary forest soils consistently exhibited lower dispersion indices and relatively better structural condition, highlighting the protective role of minimal disturbance and continuous organic inputs.

The observed variability in degradation indices is strongly supported by soil physical properties. Bulk density and total porosity, as illustrated in Figures 1 and 2, reveal clear differences in soil compaction across land use systems. Higher bulk density values were recorded in industrial and residential land uses, particularly RL II and IL II, with values approaching 1.75 Mg m⁻³, indicating severe compaction likely resulting from prolonged anthropogenic disturbance and mechanical

Limitation	RWF	Texture	BD (Mgm-3)	pH	TP (%)	SOC (g/kg)	T. N (%)	Avail. P (mgkg-1)	CEC (cmol/kg)	Ca: Mg	Al. Sat (%)	B.Sat (%)	ESP (%)
None	1	Loam	<1.3	7-8	> 50	5-10	> 0.15	> 19	> 15	> 6:1	<5	> 60	<5
Slight	2	Silt Loam, Silt Clay	1.3-1.4	6-7 or 8-9	45-50	3-5	0.10-0.15	15-19	10-15	4:1-6:1	5-10	50-60	5-10
Moderate	3	Clay Loam, Sandy Loam	1.4-1.5	5.5-5.9 or 9-9.5	40-45	1.0-3	0.05-0.10	10-15	5-10	2:1-4:1	10-15	40-50	10-15
Severe	4	Silt Clay, Loamy Sand	1.5-1.6	5.0-5.4 or >9.5	35-40	0.5-1.0	0.02-0.05	5-10	3-5	1:1 - 2:1	15-25	20-40	15-25
Extreme	5	Clay, Sand	> 1.6	<5 and > 9.5	<35	<0.5	<0.02	<5	<3	< 1.1	> 25	< 20	>25

RWF: Relative weight factor; BD: Bulk density; TP: Total porosity; SOC: Soil Organic Carbon; TN: Total Nitrogen; Avail. P: Available Phosphorus; CEC: Cation Exchange Capacity; Ca: Mg: Calcium Magnesium ratio; Al. Sat: Aluminum Saturation; B. Sat: Base Saturation; ESP: Exchangeable Sodium Percent. (Source: Lal, 1994)

Table 2: Mean Soil Degradation indices under different land use systems

Land Use	DR	CDR	CFI	CDI	S
OP I	0.77	0.56	0.64	0.36	0.45
OP II	0.74	0.63	0.61	0.39	0.40
SF I	0.75	0.59	0.63	0.37	0.72
SF II	0.68	0.56	0.64	0.36	0.69
IL I	0.76	0.68	0.59	0.41	0.29
IL II	0.76	0.71	0.59	0.41	0.22
RL I	0.63	0.48	0.68	0.32	0.32
RL II	0.58	0.49	0.67	0.33	0.27

DR= dispersion ratio, CDR=Clay dispersion ratio, CFI = Clay flocculation index, CDI = Clay dispersion index, S = Soil structural stability index

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pressure³². In contrast, secondary forest (SF I and SF II) and oil palm systems exhibited lower bulk density values, with greater variability observed in forest soils, reflecting heterogeneity associated with biological activity and organic matter accumulation. A corresponding trend was observed for soil porosity, where forest land uses maintained higher porosity levels, while residential systems, especially RL II showed consistently lower porosity, indicative of reduced pore space and impaired aeration³⁴. These patterns confirm that increased compaction leads to reduced pore connectivity, limiting water infiltration, root proliferation, and overall soil functionality. The soil structural stability index (S) ranged from 0.22 to 0.72 across all land use systems, remaining far below the threshold for stable soils, thereby indicating severe structural degradation²⁵. The lowest S values were recorded in industrial and residential soils, reflecting advanced stages of physical degradation associated with repeated disturbance and surface sealing. The inverse relationship observed between dispersion indices (DR and CDI) and S underscores the dominant role of dispersion processes in controlling soil structural integrity.

The relationship between soil organic carbon and structural stability is further illustrated in Figure 3, which shows a strong positive linear association between organic carbon content and the structural stability index. Data points across different land uses cluster closely around the regression line, demonstrated that higher organic carbon levels significantly enhance soil aggregation and stability. This finding reinforces the critical role of organic matter as a binding agent that promotes aggregate formation and resistance to structural breakdown, particularly in tropical soils.

Table 3: Mean soil physicochemical properties under different land use systems

Landuse	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Texture	BD (Mgm-3)	TP (%)	pH	SOC (g/kg)	T. N (%)	Avail. P (mgkg-1)	CEC (cmol/kg)	Al. Sat (%)	B. Sat (%)	ESP (%)	SAR
OPI	78.40	5.20	16.40	SCL	1.40	43.14	4.50	0.63	0.08	0.59	5.92	5.30	34.54	2.41	0.14
OPII	79.10	4.80	16.10	SCL	1.41	44.15	4.80	0.58	0.06	0.53	5.31	5.25	42.61	2.11	0.11
SFI	75.20	7.40	17.40	SCL	1.39	47.70	4.78	1.01	0.10	0.60	5.87	17.36	44.22	2.94	0.16
SFII	76.80	6.50	16.70	SCL	1.40	45.45	4.86	1.00	0.13	0.54	5.75	19.92	45.09	4.33	0.24
ILI	73.10	8.20	18.70	SCL	1.64	38.16	5.03	0.39	0.04	0.27	5.28	24.06	37.89	2.62	0.15
ILII	74.50	7.60	17.90	SCL	1.70	36.16	4.93	0.34	0.05	0.37	4.64	21.32	40.59	3.40	0.19
RLI	74.90	7.10	18.00	SCL	1.69	37.16	5.12	0.54	0.03	0.38	4.85	22.66	44.53	4.14	0.21
RLII	72.80	8.70	18.50	SCL	1.73	35.16	5.34	0.48	0.04	0.43	4.57	23.89	44.95	2.73	0.14

OP = Oil Palm Plantation; SF = Secondary Forest; IL = Industrial Layout; RL = Residential Layout; SCL = Sandy Clay Loam; BD = Bulk Density; TP = Total Porosity; SOC = Soil Organic Carbon; TN = Total Nitrogen; Avail. P = Available Phosphorus; CEC = Cation Exchange Capacity; Al. Sat = Aluminum Saturation; B. Sat = Base Saturation; ESP = Exchangeable Sodium Percentage, SAR = Sodium adsorption ratio

Table 4: Mean soil physicochemical properties under different land use systems

Landuse	Texture	BD (Mgm-3)	TP (%)	pH	SOC (g/kg)	T. N (%)	Avail. P (mgkg-1)	CEC (cmol/kg)	Al. Sat (%)	B. Sat (%)	ESP (%)	SAR	Mean RWF	
OPI	3	2	2	5	4	3	5	3	2	4	1	1	3	Moderate
OPII	3	2	2	5	4	3	5	3	2	3	1	1	3	moderate
SFI	3	2	2	5	4	2	5	3	4	3	1	1	3	Moderate
SFII	3	2	2	5	4	2	5	3	4	3	1	1	3	Moderate
ILI	3	5	4	5	5	5	5	3	4	4	1	1	4	Severe
ILII	3	5	4	5	5	4	5	3	4	3	1	1	3	Moderate
RLI	3	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	3	1	1	3	moderate
RLII	3	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	4	3	1	1	3	moderate

BD = bulk density, TP = total porosity, SOC = soil organic carbon, T.N = total nitrogen, CEC= cation exchange capacity, Al. Sat = aluminum saturation, BS = base saturation, ESP = exchangeable sodium percent, SAR = Sodium adsorption ratio, RWF: Relative weight factor, SDR rating: 1 = none, 2 = slight, 3 = moderate, 4 = severe, 5 = extreme The patterns observed in degradation indices are further corroborated by the physicochemical properties presented in Table 3. Industrial and residential soils recorded higher bulk density (1.64–1.73 Mg m⁻³) and lower total porosity (35.16–38.16%), confirming significant compaction. In contrast, secondary

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forest soils maintained lower bulk density ($1.39\text{--}1.40\text{ Mg m}^{-3}$) and higher porosity, reflecting better structural condition and soil functionality. These findings are consistent with established relationships between compaction, pore space reduction, and soil degradation.

Soil organic carbon (SOC) showed a marked decline from secondary forest ($1.00\text{--}1.01\text{ g kg}^{-1}$) to industrial soils ($0.34\text{--}0.39\text{ g kg}^{-1}$), emphasizing its central role in maintaining soil structure. Organic matter contributes to aggregate stability through biological binding agents and organo-mineral interactions. The strong correspondence between low SOC and high dispersion indices confirms that organic matter depletion is a primary driver of structural degradation in the study area.

Soil chemical properties further reflect the degraded condition of intensively used land systems. Soil pH ranged from 4.50 to 5.34, indicating moderately acidic conditions across all land uses. Industrial and residential soils exhibited relatively higher aluminum saturation (up to 23.89%), which may impose constraints on root development and nutrient uptake. The generally low cation exchange capacity ($4.57\text{--}5.92\text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$) highlights the limited nutrient retention capacity of Coastal Plain Sands. These chemical limitations, when combined with physical degradation, significantly reduce soil productivity.

Fig. 1: Variation in Bulk Density Across Land Use Systems

Fig 2: Soil Porosity Distribution

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Fig 3: Relationship between Organic Carbon and Structural Stability (S)

Fig. 4: Correlation Matrix of Soil Degradation Indices

Exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP: 2.11–4.33%) and sodium adsorption ratio (SAR: 0.11–0.24) remained below critical sodicity thresholds²⁵, indicating that sodium-induced dispersion is not the dominant degradation mechanism. Instead, the high dispersion indices observed are primarily associated with structural breakdown driven by compaction and organic matter depletion³⁴. This distinction is crucial, as it redirects management priorities toward improving soil structure and organic matter rather than addressing sodicity.

The integration of soil properties and degradation indices into the Soil Degradation Rating (SDR) framework provides a comprehensive assessment of soil quality across land uses (Table 4). Industrial soils were predominantly classified within the severe degradation category (SDR = 4), while residential and oil palm systems exhibited moderate degradation levels (SDR = 3). Secondary forest soils showed comparatively lower degradation status, although some degree of vulnerability remains (SDR = 3). The observed degradation gradient—secondary forest < oil palm plantation < residential layout < industrial layout—clearly reflects increasing land use intensity and anthropogenic disturbance.

Correlation analysis (Figure 4) further highlights the interdependence among soil properties and degradation indices. Strong positive relationships were observed between ESP and SAR ($r = 0.98$), as well as between CDR and CDI ($r = 0.99$), indicating closely linked

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processes. Conversely, CFI exhibited a strong inverse relationship with CDI ($r = -1.00$) and CDR ($r = -0.99$), reflecting the opposing roles of flocculation and dispersion in soil structural dynamics. Other variables, such as the structural stability index (S), showed weak correlations, suggesting that structural stability is influenced by multiple interacting factors beyond individual indices.

CONCLUSION

From a functional perspective, the observed degradation patterns have significant implications for soil productivity and ecosystem services. Compacted and structurally unstable soils restrict root penetration, reduce infiltration, and increase susceptibility to erosion, ultimately limiting crop performance and land sustainability. Low nutrient availability and high aluminum saturation further exacerbate these constraints, particularly in intensively used systems. The SDR framework therefore serves as an effective tool for translating complex soil data into actionable insights for land management. Results demonstrate that soil degradation in the Coastal Plain Sands of southeastern Nigeria is primarily driven by land use-induced compaction and organic matter depletion. The multi-indicator approach adopted in this study effectively captures the complexity of degradation processes and provides a robust basis for soil quality assessment and sustainable land management in fragile tropical ecosystems.

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